

PROGRESS IN SOLAR ENERGY: FROM TECHNOLOGICAL INNOVATION TO POLICY CONSEQUENCES

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ABSTRACT

The world local area has moved its concentration to environmentally friendly power sources in the objective of supportable turn of events, with sun oriented energy arising as a significant subject of interest. This record offers a careful rundown of flow improvements in the field of sun powered energy research, including mechanical forward leaps, strategy consequences, and evaluations of the venture's financial practicality. The article starts with an assessment of the Reasonable Advancement Objectives (SDGs) laid out by the Assembled Countries. It then, at that point, underlines how significant sunlight-based energy is to relieving environmental change, propelling civil rights, and making financial development. Energy access is utilized to investigations the shift to sustainable power sources, with an emphasis on smart electrical organizations and decentralized energy frameworks. From that point onward, the paper investigates the numerous sorts of photovoltaic/warm (PV/T) gatherers, going over their plan ideas and productivity factors. Besides, it looks at various exploration drives, going from the formation of mixture sun powered energy frameworks to the practicality of sun based energy creation financially in different settings. The examination accentuates how assorted sun powered energy research is and that it is so vital to lessening a dangerous atmospheric devotion and accomplishing manageable improvement targets. The article closes with ideas for future review and strategy, upholding for the quick reception of clean energy innovation to satisfy the world's rising energy requests in a reasonable manner.

Keywords: Solar energy, sustainable development, photovoltaic/thermal collectors, renewable energy, policy analysis, economic feasibility, technological innovation, climate change mitigation

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1. INTRODUCTION

Maintainable turn of events, which the United Nations has embraced by taking on 17 Sustainable Development Objectives (SDGs), has turned into a need in the cutting-edge world. With an accentuation on orientation correspondence, social consideration, the destruction of neediness, ecological security, and the advancement of harmony and thriving, these objectives try to address various worldwide issues[1]. Remarkably, representing practically 60% of ozone harming substance outflows, the energy business contributes fundamentally to environmental change. SDG-7 spotlights on giving networks from one side of the planet to the other admittance to modest, clean energy while advancing venture and advancement in the different periods of energy creation and dissemination [2].

The level of individuals overall who approach power has expanded by 6.2% over the most recent decade, with rustic networks seeing a 13.2% expansion starting around 2010. The Global Environmentally friendly power Organization's (IREA) 2020 review, nonetheless, accentuates that 0.8 billion individuals actually need admittance to drive starting around 2018, despite headways [2]. Decentralized or conveyed energy frameworks are turning out to be more famous due to well established financial and administration issues with customary lattice-based energy frameworks. These frameworks present reasonable ways of expanding energy access as a result of their ability to deal with the energy trilemma, which comprises of expenses, discharges, and security [3].

Be that as it may, when appropriated energy sources become all the more broadly utilized, new issues for electrical dispersion networks emerge, similar to invert power stream. This calls for changes to customary power framework structures, highlighting the meaning of shrewd electrical frameworks in taking care of the changing organization conditions [4]. At various mechanical status levels (TRLs), there are currently around 400 innovation plans and parts focused on at bringing down CO₂ outflows. Among these choices are sun based energy advancements, for example, photovoltaics (PV) and sun oriented warm, which might give intensity and power both now and again the lattice [5].

Various causes, for example, the dropping expense of sustainable power, the need to cut fossil fuel byproducts, expanded energy security, all-inclusive energy access, the making of occupations, and monetary advantages, are pushing the worldwide create some distance from petroleum derivatives and towards sustainable power sources. As per reports, for sustainable power to represent 65% of the fundamental energy supply by 2050, a sum of USD 29 trillion in speculations should be made [6]. By 2050, as indicated by the Global Environmentally friendly power Organization (IREA), 86% of power produced would come from inexhaustible sources, with 360 GW of sun-oriented PV expected to be introduced yearly. Three significant private PV development markets are Europe, the US, and China [7].

By 2030 and 2050, solar PV is predicted to provide 13% and 25% of the world's electricity needs, respectively, with distributed solar energy accounting for 40% of this total. Growth is anticipated in solar thermal, which now provides 7% of the world's heat needs, especially in space heating applications. In an effort to cut emissions, the European Union has set high goals for the percentage of renewable energy, increasing energy efficiency, and lowering greenhouse gas emissions [8].

Accelerating the adoption of clean energy technology through various interventions is the goal in order to meet power, heating, and cooling demands in a sustainable manner. Novel approaches to district heating and cooling networks are being investigated, including heat pumps, solar thermal, and geothermal. But there are obstacles, like limitations to social and aesthetic acceptance, especially in urban areas and historic sites [9]. It is imperative to support real-world demonstration projects that take techno-economic, legal, and social concerns into account. Initiatives like as the Interreg 2 Seas SOLARISE project are designed to showcase

emerging technology and investigate their effects, encouraging the use of solar power in old structures and low-income homes [10].

Buildings account for 80% of the final energy consumption in the European Union, which is largely attributed to heating and cooling. Buildings' space heating and water heating systems account for 40% and 17% of total energy use, respectively. Even with this high demand for energy, only 22% of the energy needed for heating and cooling comes from renewable sources at the moment, with fossil fuels still providing 75% of the supply [11].

The EU is exploring digitization efforts in the building industry and energy systems in order to address this. Building digitalization offers a chance to increase energy efficiency and reach untapped markets. Some EU nations have witnessed notable increases in residential and commercial photovoltaic capacity, while others have prioritized utility-scale solar installations due to enticing feed-in tariff schemes [11].

Well-connected communities are fostered by the integration of distributed energy technologies and high-capacity renewables made possible by the development of smart grids and smart-ready buildings. The European Commission (EC) supports member states' decisions regarding their energy mix and is aware of the risks to energy security posed by the growing use of renewable energy sources. A few members have chosen to incorporate nuclear energy, which is regarded as a clean and base load energy source, into their national energy plans [11].

With an emphasis on energy efficiency, the EU hopes to establish itself as a leader in renewable energy. By 2050, electricity is expected to account for 53% of total energy consumption; nevertheless, in order to attain net zero greenhouse gas emissions, there will need to be a major increase in the production of renewable electricity [8]. According to a recent report (Figure 1), the power generation mix would consist of 86% renewable energy by 2050, with solar photovoltaics (PV) emerging as the dominant source of installed power capacity [12].

Figure 1. Part of each category in the overall solar PV capacity of the EU's chosen nations [13]

A number of roadmap studies and projection studies show how the energy system will change from being heavily dependent on traditional fuels with high operating costs to one with larger initial capital investments and lower fuel costs over time. Infrastructural upgrades are required

to enable greater integration of renewable energy sources to meet the demands for power, heating, and cooling. The decarbonization goals of the transportation sector, especially with regard to the use of electric vehicles, are anticipated to increase the share of electricity in final energy demand [14].

Despite a slowdown in China, the global solar PV market experienced significant growth in 2019, with PV generation increasing by 22%. This growth was partially offset by China's decision to discontinue feed-in tariffs, focusing instead on cost control and grid integration challenges. In contrast, stable solar PV growth was observed in the United States, supported by federal tax incentives and state-level policies [15].

2. TYPES OF PVT COLLECTORS

PV/T collectors come in a variety of forms, including water-based, air-based, and hybrids that use both water and air as heat transfer fluids (Figure 2). Water-based PVT collectors are preferred because of their better heat conductivity than air, which is related to their increased efficiency [16]. But because they are more affordable and can be quickly converted from PV collectors to PVT collectors with little modifications, air-based PVT collectors are more often used. PV panels, which transform solar radiation into electrical energy, absorber plates, and insulating materials are the main parts of PV collectors. By absorbing excess heat, the thermal absorber beneath the module lowers the temperature of the PV panel and increases its electrical efficiency [17].

Figure 2. Classifications of PVT collectors

This simultaneous generation of electricity and thermal energy results in higher exergy and greater energy efficiency compared to standalone solar thermal or PV systems. Studies by Adnan et al. have shown that spiral absorber collectors exhibit the highest energy efficiency at 64% compared to other designs. Additionally, maintaining an adequate mass flow rate is crucial for optimizing PV/T collector performance. Figure (3) shows Cross-section of different types of PVT collectors [18].

Figure 3. Cross-section through several PVT collector types. There are several different types of air-based PVT collectors: (a) single pass; (b) double pass; (c) fin-equipped; (d) v-groove absorber; and (e) round tube absorber [19].

3. WATER-BASED PVT SYSTEMS

The way that PV modules and thermal absorbers are integrated has a big impact on how efficient PV/T water systems are. These systems have quite high electrical efficiency, ranging from 6.7% to 15%, because they usually use crystalline silicon cells. However, the design of the system and its working environment have a significant impact on thermal efficiency, which vary from 22% to 79% [20]. The most popular varieties of PV/T water collectors are shown schematically in Figure (4), including hybrid collectors with tubes and channels that may or may not have protective glass covering them, as well as collectors with water channels situated either above or below the PV module [21].

In addition to the PV module, thermal absorber, and optional glazing cover, adhesives (such as EVA with tedlar-polyester-tedlar layers) and insulation are also necessary. Hybrid systems function similarly to matching flat solar thermal collectors, with both forced and natural circulation (thermosiphon) [22].

Figure 4. Diagrammatic cross section of a PV/T water collector showing the tubes, channels, water channels above and below the PV module [21].

The PV/T framework with regular water flow is comprised of a sun-based kettle and a level PV/T gatherer. The authority's feedback and result pipes are promptly associated with the intensity exchanger of the sun-based kettle. Water circles normally after the shut planetary group is loaded up with water. Cooler water gets back to the gatherer while warmed water from the assortment ascends to the intensity exchanger of the sun powered kettle since it is heavier. However long there is a temperature contrast between the water in the evaporator and the gatherer, brought about by sun-oriented radiation, this normal dissemination will proceed. A schematic design of the PV/T framework with normal water flow is displayed in Figure (5). It incorporates a water-warming framework and a flatbox aluminum-combination PV module with single-translucent Si cells [23].

Figure 5. PV/T system schematic diagram with natural water circulation [24].

The thermal collector and a water tank that is placed horizontally on an Al-alloy bracket are important parts. Compared to other collector designs, this design has benefits like a wide contact surface that promotes effective heat exchange and a consistent temperature distribution throughout the collector width [25]. The PV module, converter, accumulator batteries, switches, wiring, and devices for measuring temperature and irradiance include electric thermometers and pyranometers. With a PV module coverage factor of 0.63, this system achieves a daily electrical efficiency of roughly 10.15% and a daily thermal efficiency of over 45%. This results in a daily total efficiency that exceeds 52% and a daily primary energy-saving efficiency of up to 65% [26].

The schematic graph of a PV/T framework with constrained water course is displayed in Figure (6). It incorporates each of the vital associations for water flow inside the shut nearby planet group, as well as a conventional sheet-and-cylinder PV/T water gatherer, a sun powered water radiator, a course siphon, a calorimeter, a pyranometer, and a simple to-computerized (A/D) converter [27]. The framework's constrained water dissemination is kept up with by the course siphon, which has a differential indoor regulator and can be initiated physically or consequently. At the point when the temperature differential between the sun oriented water warmer and gatherer arrives at a specific level, for example, 5 to 15°C, the differential indoor regulator, which controls water temperature in both, enacts the dissemination siphon [28].

Figure 6. Schematic diagram of PV/T system with forced water circulation: (1) hot water storage, (2) pump, (3) valve, (4) calorimeter, (5) A/D converter, (6) pyranometer and (7) computer.

Within the closed circuit, an expansion vessel maintains the proper water pressure; in the event that the pressure lowers, water is supplied from the network. While a calorimeter measures thermal energy and the water heater's mass flow rate, electrical thermometers measure the input and output temperatures from the PV/T collector as well as the water's temperature [29]. A battery charge regulator directs generated electrical energy into the battery, which is then provided to consumers via a DC/AC converter. When joined with a miniature regulator, the A/D converter empowers computerized estimations of voltage, current, temperature, and different factors. It can likewise be connected to a PC for programming control [30].

4. RELATED WORKS

The table (1) gives an exhaustive synopsis of the many examination projects that have been completed in the field of sunlight-based energy, with an accentuation on a scope of subjects including strategy investigation, framework streamlining, execution assessment, monetary possibility, and innovation improvement. Each study project handles specific issues or prospects concerning the utilization of sunlight based energy and gives savvy data on how it very well may be applied in different regions and businesses.

Table 1. Related Works Analysis

Researchers	Problem Statement	Objectives	Results	Strength Points	Limitation
[31]	Western region of Saudi Arabia faces energy challenges	Analyze hybrid PV/diesel system implementation	Impact assessment, comparison of system configurations	Reduced energy cost, enhanced security, scalability	Integration of PV reduces dependency, comprehensive analysis
[32]	Need for solar cooling technologies	Investigate TEACS performance driven by PV	Influence of input current, model development, feasibility evaluation	Sustainable solution, technological innovation	Real-time data integration, environmental benefits
[33]	Lack of electricity access in Rwanda	Identify new technology needs, design renewable energy systems	Cost-effective hybrid selection, applicability assessment	Scalability, real-time data utilization	Transferability, cost-effectiveness focus
[34]	Importance of solar-powered air conditioners	Develop computational model, optimize solar on-grid system	Model validation, economic feasibility assessment	Environmental impact, climate sensitivity analysis	Rigorous validation, economic viability
[35]	Comparison of solar hybrid AC with conventional units	Evaluate performance, assess energy savings potential	Development of analytical solutions, highlighting advantages	Energy efficiency, technological advancement	Comprehensive analysis, contribution to innovation
[36]	Thermal effectiveness of hybrid AC system in Nasiriyah, Iraq	Assess thermal effectiveness, evaluate solar heater placement	Different placement affects system efficiency, increased energy savings	Addresses energy efficiency, technological innovation	Limited scope, lack of long-term data
[37]	Energy savings in academic institutions	Investigate energy consumption, conduct energy audit, assess rooftop solar integration	Identified major energy consumers, potential for significant savings with solar	Relevant to sustainability, actionable recommendations	Scope limitation, lack of detailed methodology
[38]	Mathematical models for HVAC systems using nanofluids	Create models, explore impact of various factors	Nanofluid enhances system performance, comprehensive analysis	Technological innovation, computational efficiency	Limited experimental validation, computational complexity

[39]	Optimal sizing of solar hydrogen hybrid system for houses	Determine optimal component sizing, ensure uninterrupted power supply	Guarantees reliable power supply, energy independence	Site-specific applicability, reliability	Simplified analysis, lack of long-term analysis
[40]	Viability of solar-assisted ground-coupled heat pump (SAGCHP)	Develop and simulate SAGCHP combinations	Identified viable SAGCHP combination, reduced ground thermal imbalance	Renewable energy integration, climate-specific analysis	Simulation-based analysis, lack of economic analysis
[41]	Performance analysis of PEMFC-based distributed generation system	Establish system, highlight significant findings	PEMFC-based DG met 46.44% energy demand, encouraging for future research	Practical application, empirical validation	Limited scope, lack of long-term analysis, lack of comprehensive analysis
[42]	Hybrid solar system combining PV panels and air thermal collectors	Develop model, test efficiency under Romanian climatic conditions	Increased electric power output by 7.905%, effective thermal energy recovery	Dual functionality, climate suitability	Limited scope, lack of long-term analysis, lack of economic analysis
[43]	Solar hybrid air conditioner development	Develop an affordable air-conditioning system	Achieved 45-71% solar fraction, reduced CO2 emissions	Environmental impact, technical analysis	Lack of comprehensive analysis, scalability analysis, economic analysis
[44]	Solar energy expansion barriers in Iran and solar power plant simulation	Analyze barriers to solar energy expansion, simulate solar power plants	Identified expansion barriers, simulated plant performance	Comprehensive analysis, policy implications	Regional focus, simulation limitations, lack of qualitative analysis
[45]	Performance evaluation of a small-capacity DC refrigerator for solar refrigeration	Develop a thermodynamic model, compare refrigerants and heat exchanger effectiveness	R290 and R600a have higher COP, recommended heat exchanger effectiveness values	Technical analysis, practical recommendations	Simplified assumptions, lack of real-world validation, simplified modeling approach
[46]	Evaluation of Hybrid Solar Power Systems (HSPS) in Southern Nigeria	Assess HSPS performance in urban-residential and healthcare sectors	Hybrid configurations with SPV integration outperform standalone DPG systems	Holistic evaluation, comparative analysis	Limited sample size, lack of detailed technical analysis
[47]	Economic feasibility of solar energy generation in Vietnamese households	Assess economic viability of solar energy generation	Identifies weaknesses in Vietnam's solar power policy	Regional assessment, policy recommendations	Software limitations, data limitations

[48]	Optimal sizing of Floating Solar Photovoltaic Systems (FSPV) for rural micro-grid electrification	Analyze feasibility and optimal sizing of FSPV systems	FSPV systems generate higher energy output than land-based PV systems	Increased power output, comparative analysis	Site-specific considerations, modeling assumptions, technological constraints
[49]	Development and commercialization potential of PVT-PCM technology	Provide overview and assess commercialization potential	Promising performance of PVT-PCM technology, China's leadership role	Comprehensive analysis, strategic recommendations	Lack of industry adoption, regional focus
[50]	Hybrid multi-generation photovoltaic leaf concept	Develop and demonstrate effectiveness	Reduced cell temperature, increased electrical efficiency, multi-generation capabilities	Innovative concept, experimental demonstration	Application limitations, practical challenges
[51]	Grid-connected hybrid renewable energy system for a hotel in Petra, Jordan	Conduct comprehensive analysis and optimization	Significant reductions in energy costs and carbon emissions	Comprehensive analysis, practical application	Specific context, simplified assumptions, economic factors
[52]	Reliability assessment of solar PV systems for off-grid island households in Cebu, Philippines	Assess reliability and performance	PV system can meet current electrical demand, but future demand considerations needed	Practical relevance, comprehensive analysis	Limited scope, assumptions, future demand considerations

The exploration projects that are assembled in the table exhibit the multi-layered character of sunlight-based energy research and its significance in handling the world's energy issues. This examination further the information and use of sunlight-based energy innovation by addressing hardships connected with energy access in emerging countries and upgrading sun-oriented energy frameworks for specific purposes.

The turn of events and improvement of crossover sunlight-based energy frameworks — which consolidate photovoltaic (PV) innovation with other environmentally friendly power sources or regular energy frameworks like climate control systems or diesel generators — has been the subject of a few examinations. These half breed frameworks are fitting for a scope of uses, including the business, modern, and private areas since they give expanded proficiency, reliability, and cost-viability.

Furthermore, a typical subject in many examinations is the monetary suitability of sun-oriented energy age. Analysts look at the monetary manageability of sun-oriented ventures and pinpoint reception bottlenecks. Through assessment of sunlight-based energy's financial likely in different areas and conditions, these examinations offer wise data to energy partners, financial backers, and controllers.

Moreover, innovative headways like sunlight-based refrigeration frameworks, sun oriented controlled heat siphons, and sun powered cooled innovation show the range of purposes for sunlight-based energy beyond the creation of power. These improvements offer practical

answers for refrigeration, warming, and cooling prerequisites in various settings as well as bringing down fossil fuel byproducts.

The discoveries additionally accentuate that it is so urgent to take environment awareness, adaptability, and ecological impacts into account while creating and sending sunlight-based energy frameworks. Specialists try to progress maintainable energy arrangements that diminish environmental change and further develop energy security by surveying the ecological benefits, environment strength, and versatility of sunlight-based innovations.

In light of everything, the consequences of these examinations add to the extending corpus of information on sun powered energy and deal wise data to specialists, lawmakers, and business experts who need to expand sun-oriented energy's true capacity for a feasible future.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The extensive variety of examination drives analyzed in this study shows the intricacy of sun-based energy research and its significance in handling the world's energy issues. These examinations advance our comprehension and utilization of sun powered energy innovation in various areas and geological regions, from mechanical headways to strategy assessments. The outcomes feature how critically we should speed up the shift to environmentally friendly power sources to diminish a worldwide temperature alteration, further develop energy security, and advance economical turn of events. It will be vital to subsidize multidisciplinary research projects later on that join strategy investigation, monetary practicality assessments, and specialized development. We can introduce a more feasible and impartial energy future for people in the future by completely utilizing sun powered energy.

REFERENCES

- [1] António Guterres, "The Sustainable Development Goals Report 2019," United Nations Publ. issued by Dep. Econ. Soc. Aff., vol. 10, pp. 1–64, 2019.
- [2] A. G. Olabi et al., "Wind Energy Contribution to the Sustainable Development Goals: Case Study on London Array," *Sustain.*, vol. 15, no. 5, 2023, doi: 10.3390/su15054641.
- [3] M. J. Barasa Kabeyi, "Decentralized and Distributed Power Generation," *Proc. 5th African Int. Conf. Ind. Eng. Oper. Manag. Decentralized*, no. December, 2023, doi: 10.46254/ap04.20230268.
- [4] K. A. Makinde, D. O. Akinyele, and A. O. Amole, "Voltage rise problem in distribution networks with distributed generation: A review of technologies, impact and mitigation approaches," *Indones. J. Electr. Eng. Informatics*, vol. 9, no. 3, pp. 575–600, 2021, doi: 10.52549/V9I3.2971.
- [5] A. Boretti, "Technology Readiness Level of Solar Thermochemical Splitting Cycles," *ACS Energy Lett.*, vol. 6, pp. 1170–1174, Mar. 2021, doi: 10.1021/acsenerylett.1c00181.
- [6] W. Strielkowski, E. Tarkhanova, M. Tvaronavič, and Y. Petrenko, "Renewable Energy in the Sustainable Development of Electrical," *Energies*, vol. 14, pp. 1–24, 2021.
- [7] M. Larsson, *Global energy transformation: Four necessary steps to make clean energy the next success story*. 2009. doi: 10.1057/9780230244092.
- [8] I. Tsiropoulos, W. Nijs, D. Tarvydas, and P. Ruiz Castello, *Towards net-zero emissions in the EU energy system by 2050*. 2020. doi: 10.2760/081488.
- [9] L. Chen et al., *Green building practices to integrate renewable energy in the construction sector: a review*, vol. 22, no. 2. Springer International Publishing, 2024. doi: 10.1007/s10311-023-01675-2.
- [10] N. Bertelsen et al., *Integrating low-temperature renewables in district energy systems: Guidelines for policy makers*. 2021.
- [11] Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Energy (BMWi), "Comprehensive assessment of the potential for efficient heating and cooling for Germany," *IREES*, vol. 14, no. 1, 2020.

- [12] Singapore Energy Market Authority, “Charting the Energy Transition to 2050: Energy 2050 Committee Report,” no. March, 2022.
- [13] A. Alazazmeh, A. Ahmed, M. Siddiqui, and M. Asif, “Real-time data-based performance analysis of a large-scale building applied PV system,” *Energy Reports*, vol. 8, pp. 15408–15420, 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.egy.2022.11.057.
- [14] K. Handayani, Y. Krozer, and T. Filatova, “From fossil fuels to renewables: An analysis of long-term scenarios considering technological learning,” *Energy Policy*, vol. 127, no. January 2018, pp. 134–146, 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.enpol.2018.11.045.
- [15] C. Dong, R. Zhou, and J. Li, “Rushing for subsidies: The impact of feed-in tariffs on solar photovoltaic capacity development in China,” *Appl. Energy*, vol. 281, p. 116007, Jan. 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.apenergy.2020.116007.
- [16] Z. U. Abdin and A. Rachid, “A survey on applications of hybrid pv/t panels,” *Energies*, vol. 14, no. 4, 2021, doi: 10.3390/en14041205.
- [17] O. El Manssouri, B. Hajji, G. M. Tina, A. Gagliano, and S. Aneli, “Electrical and thermal performances of Bi-fluid PV/thermal collectors,” *Energies*, vol. 14, no. 6, 2021, doi: 10.3390/en14061633.
- [18] M. Herrando et al., “A review of solar hybrid photovoltaic-thermal (PV-T) collectors and systems,” *Prog. Energy Combust. Sci.*, vol. 97, no. January, p. 101072, 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.pecs.2023.101072.
- [19] M. Mustapha, A. Fudholi, C. H. Yen, M. H. Ruslan, and K. Sopian, “Review on energy and exergy analysis of air and water based photovoltaic thermal (PVT) collector,” *Int. J. Power Electron. Drive Syst.*, vol. 9, no. 3, pp. 1367–1373, 2018, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v9.i3.pp1367-1373.
- [20] K. Moradi, M. Ali Ebadian, and C. X. Lin, “A review of PV/T technologies: Effects of control parameters,” *Int. J. Heat Mass Transf.*, vol. 64, pp. 483–500, 2013, doi: 10.1016/j.ijheatmasstransfer.2013.04.044.
- [21] L. T. Kostić and J. S. Aleksić, “Review of research, development and application of photovoltaic/thermal water systems,” *Open Phys.*, vol. 18, no. 1, pp. 1025–1047, 2020, doi: 10.1515/phys-2020-0213.
- [22] T. Ma, M. Li, and A. Kazemian, “Photovoltaic thermal module and solar thermal collector connected in series to produce electricity and high-grade heat simultaneously,” *Appl. Energy*, vol. 261, p. 114380, Mar. 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.apenergy.2019.114380.
- [23] X. Cao, N. Li, Y. Li, L. Che, B. Yu, and H. Liu, “A review of photovoltaic/thermal (PV/T) technology applied in building environment control,” *Energy Built Environ.*, 2023, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbenv.2023.12.003>.
- [24] H. B. C. El Hocine, K. Touafek, F. Kerrou, H. Haloui, and A. Khelifa, “Model Validation of an Empirical Photovoltaic Thermal (PV/T) Collector,” *Energy Procedia*, vol. 74, pp. 1090–1099, 2015, doi: 10.1016/j.egypro.2015.07.749.
- [25] F. Ardente, G. Beccali, M. Cellura, and V. Lo Brano, “Life cycle assessment of a solar thermal collector,” *Renew. Energy*, vol. 30, no. 7, pp. 1031–1054, 2005, doi: 10.1016/j.renene.2004.09.009.
- [26] M. Khan, N. Ibrahim, M. M. Islam, H. Ali, S. Rahman, and F. Al-Sulaiman, “Evaluation of solar collector designs with integrated latent heat thermal energy storage: A review,” *Sol. Energy*, vol. 166, May 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.solener.2018.03.014.
- [27] M. Ibrahim, D. Abdulsalam, D. Kulla, S. Umaru, and I. Enagi, “a Retrofitted Photovoltaic Thermal (Pv/T) System for Heating and Electrification: an Experimental Approach,” *Nile J. Eng. Appl. Sci.*, no. 0, p. 1, 2023, doi: 10.5455/njeas.154532.
- [28] I. Guarracino, A. Mellor, N. J. Ekins-Daukes, and C. N. Markides, “Dynamic coupled thermal-and-electrical modelling of sheet-and-tube hybrid photovoltaic/thermal (PVT) collectors,” *Appl. Therm. Eng.*, vol. 101, no. March, pp. 778–795, 2016, doi: 10.1016/j.applthermaleng.2016.02.056.

- [29] Y. He et al., “Thermal performance and experimental analysis of stainless steel flat plate solar collector with full-flow channels,” *Heliyon*, vol. 10, no. 7, pp. 1–14, 2024, doi: 10.1016/j.heliyon.2024.e28255.
- [30] Wika instruments, “WIKA-Handbook · Pressure and Temperature Measurement U.S. Edition,” no. 770, p. 436, 2008.
- [31] M. A. M. Ramli, A. Hiendro, and H. R. E. H. Boucekara, “Performance analysis of hybrid PV/diesel energy system in western region of Saudi Arabia,” *Int. J. Photoenergy*, vol. 2014, 2014, doi: 10.1155/2014/626251.
- [32] M. M. Aboelmaaref et al., “Design and performance analysis of a thermoelectric air-conditioning system driven by solar photovoltaic panels,” *Proc. Inst. Mech. Eng. Part C J. Mech. Eng. Sci.*, vol. 235, no. 20, pp. 5146–5159, 2021, doi: 10.1177/0954406220976164.
- [33] J. D. D. Niyonteze, F. Zou, G. Norensa Osarumwense Asemota, S. Bimenyimana, and G. Shyirambere, “Key technology development needs and applicability analysis of renewable energy hybrid technologies in off-grid areas for the Rwanda power sector,” *Heliyon*, vol. 6, no. 1, p. e03300, 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.heliyon.2020.e03300.
- [34] F. J. Aguilar, J. Ruiz, M. Lucas, and P. G. Vicente, “Performance Analysis and Optimisation of a Solar On-Grid Air Conditioner,” *Energies*, vol. 14, no. 8054, 2021.
- [35] N. C. Nwasuka and U. Nwaiwu, “Performance Evaluation of a Solar Hybrid Air-Conditioner,” *Proc. Eng. Sci.*, vol. 3, no. 4, pp. 463–472, 2021, doi: 10.24874/PES03.04.010.
- [36] M. N. Saddam, “Performance Analysis of a Solar Assisted Hybrid Air-Conditioning System Worked in Hot Regions of the Iraqi Climate,” *Math. Stat. Eng. Appl.*, vol. 71, no. 4, pp. 4237–4253, 2022.
- [37] M. F. M. Zublie, M. Hasanuzzaman, and N. A. Rahim, “Energy Efficiency and Feasibility Analysis of Solar Power Generation Using Hybrid System of an Educational Institution in Malaysia,” *Int. J. Photoenergy*, vol. 2023, pp. 8–10, 2023, doi: 10.1155/2023/1673512.
- [38] W. Jamshed et al., “Solar energy optimization in solar-HVAC using Sutterby hybrid nanofluid with Smoluchowski temperature conditions: a solar thermal application,” *Sci. Rep.*, vol. 12, no. 1, pp. 1–19, 2022, doi: 10.1038/s41598-022-15685-7.
- [39] C. Acar, E. Erturk, and I. Firtina-Ertis, “Performance analysis of a stand-alone integrated solar hydrogen energy system for zero energy buildings,” *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy*, vol. 48, no. 5, pp. 1664–1684, 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.ijhydene.2022.10.051.
- [40] A. Berkane, M. Aksas, and Z. Aouachria, “Performance Study of a Hybrid Solar-Assisted Ground-Source Heat Pump System Used for Building Heating and Hot Water Demands,” *Jordan J. Mech. Ind. Eng.*, vol. 17, no. 4, pp. 581–594, 2023, doi: 10.59038/jjmie/170413.
- [41] A. N. Akpolat, E. Dursun, and Y. Yang, “Performance Analysis of a PEMFC-Based Grid-Connected Distributed Generation System,” *Appl. Sci.*, vol. 13, no. 6, pp. 1–17, 2023, doi: 10.3390/app13063521.
- [42] S. Budea and M. Simionescu, “Solar Hybrid System for Electricity and Air Heating - Experimental Research,” *IOP Conf. Ser. Earth Environ. Sci.*, vol. 1185, no. 1, 2023, doi: 10.1088/1755-1315/1185/1/012001.
- [43] N. Uchekukwu, C. P. Nwadinobi, M. C. Chukwuma, and V. C. Nwakwuribe, “Development of a solar hybrid air conditioner,” *Indian J. Eng.*, vol. 20, no. 53, pp. 1–9, 2023, doi: 10.54905/diss/v20i53/e18ije1644.
- [44] A. Razmjoo, A. Ghazanfari, P. A. Østergaard, and S. Abedi, “Design and Analysis of Grid-Connected Solar Photovoltaic Systems for Sustainable Development of Remote Areas,” *Energies*, vol. 16, no. 7, 2023, doi: 10.3390/en16073181.
- [45] C. Amaris, F. Barbosa, and M. Balbis-Morejon, “Energy Performance Analysis of a Solar Refrigerator Using Ecological Refrigerants,” *J. Sustain. Dev. Energy, Water Environ. Syst.*, vol. 11, no. 2, pp. 1–25, 2023, doi: 10.13044/j.sdewes.d11.0446.
- [46] Z. Ismaila et al., “Evaluation of a hybrid solar power system as a potential replacement for urban residential and medical economic activity areas in southern Nigeria,” *AIMS Energy*, vol. 11, no. 2, pp. 319–336, 2023, doi: 10.3934/ENERGY.2023017.

- [47] T. D. Nguyen, H. T. H. Le, and H. M. Bui, “The Development of Solar Electric Power in Vietnam From Economy and Policy Analysis,” *Polish J. Environ. Stud.*, vol. 32, no. 5, pp. 4219–4227, 2023, doi: 10.15244/pjoes/166349.
- [48] S. Bhattacharya, A. Goswami, and P. K. Sadhu, “Design, development and performance analysis of FSPV system for powering sustainable energy based mini micro-grid,” *Microsyst. Technol.*, vol. 29, no. 10, pp. 1465–1478, 2023, doi: 10.1007/s00542-023-05457-2.
- [49] M. H. Abdul Jabar et al., “The solar end game: bibliometric analysis, research and development evolution, and patent activity of hybrid photovoltaic/thermal—phase change material,” *Environ. Sci. Pollut. Res.*, vol. 30, no. 55, pp. 116934–116951, 2023, doi: 10.1007/s11356-023-27641-7.
- [50] G. Huang, J. Xu, and C. N. Markides, “High-efficiency bio-inspired hybrid multi-generation photovoltaic leaf,” *Nat. Commun.*, vol. 14, no. 1, 2023, doi: 10.1038/s41467-023-38984-7.
- [51] H. Al-Rawashdeh et al., “Performance Analysis of a Hybrid Renewable-Energy System for Green Buildings to Improve Efficiency and Reduce GHG Emissions with Multiple Scenarios,” *Sustain.*, vol. 15, no. 9, 2023, doi: 10.3390/su15097529.
- [52] K. R. M. Supapo, L. Lozano, and E. M. Querkiol, “Performance Evaluation of an Existing Renewable Energy System at Gilutongan Island, Cebu, Philippines,” *J. Eng.*, vol. 2024, pp. 1–19, 2024, doi: 10.1155/2024/3131377.

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